

FEASIBILITY FOR SETTING UP GERIATRIC CARE SERVICES IN A TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL

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Abstract- Introduction: The Healthcare industry has identified the need for specialized clinical care for the elderly people, given to the rise in the population. The vision of making the elderly population less dependent on their family has developed multiple facilities and specializations in their favor. However, establishment of a uniform Geriatric center may not be feasible across all the health care institutions. Careful analysis and assessment of the need and well as study of the feasibility of the same is very important. This will ensure that there is optimum utilization of the established unit.

This study looks at the views of doctors and management representatives regarding the feasibility for setting up a full-fledged geriatric unit in a tertiary care teaching hospital.

Methodology: This study used questionnaires to get information from doctors and management representatives about the feasibility for setting up a Geriatric care services in the chosen tertiary care teaching hospital.

Results and Conclusion: The study showed that the majority of the doctors and management representatives agree that a geriatric unit will help in reducing functional decline. 90.4 % of the doctors and 66.4% of the management representatives agreed that a geriatric unit will help in targeting of appropriate high risk patients and if implemented successfully the hospital will receive greater recognition for the achievements made. The data also showed that the respondents had suggested a suitable location for setting up a geriatric department in a selected hospital.

Keywords: Geriatrics, Elderly Patients, Healthcare, Medical Services, aging, Operational Feasibility, Quality patient care

I: Introduction

In India the percentage of elderly population has increased in the past decades. With the increase in the number of the elderly people, the dependency rate also increases. In today's fast moving world where in the individuals are ambitious and career oriented, the individuals feel burdened to look after their old dependents. Their health care and treatment cost and time becomes a huge worry. Hence anticipating this situation, the health care sector has to implement geriatric services in the hospitals which acts as an aid to the above problem.

Although geriatric medicine and services are practiced in most of the hospitals in the developed and developing countries, India is lagging behind. With the increase in the number of elderly people in India there is a huge need for the health care sectors to set up an efficient and effective geriatric unit. The development of geriatrics and geriatric systems of care in India will not only make the elderly people independent but also increase the life style, life expectancy, quality of life and decrease the cost of care.

A hospital must address and meet the needs of the elderly people. Along with the medical care facilities, various architectural features like infrastructure, layout, lighting, colour, passageways, ventilation, furniture, interior and also the safety and security of the patients should be taken into account when setting up a geriatric unit. The unit should be set up in such a way that the patients get a homely feeling and are not tired of the hospital atmosphere during their duration of treatment. Older people often have complex care needs and may have co-morbidities that require a holistic, problem-solving approach to their care.

In order to establish and run an efficient and accurate geriatric unit there is a need to assess the various factors, requirements and feasibility of setting up the unit. Only with the proper assessment one will be able to determine the quality and cost of care that can be delivered. The selected tertiary care teaching hospital has a vision to heal and comfort the suffering humanity with compassion and respect and to be progressive in providing holistic health care

service to all. The hospital does not have a specialized geriatric set up. Comprehensive geriatric care is the need of the hour.

II: Review of literature

A geriatric consults involve assessment of physical, emotional, cognitive, and functional status in older persons. A “consult” can refer to inpatient or resident care at facilities, ranging from acute – care hospital to long term care homes, as well as to outpatient or outreach services. Regardless of age, an in-hospital stay increases the risk of infections and adverse events such as falls, but the impact of such events is far more severe among older patients. Elderly patients are often frail and require more recovery time than their younger counterparts. A geriatric consultation often deals with issues beyond the reason for admission to hospital (Lewis, 2008).

Ensuring good quality geriatric health care services at the primary level would greatly help in improving the utilization rates of the available health services. Health care services should be based on the “felt needs” of the elderly population. The felt needs may vary depending upon gender; socio-economic status as well as differences would exist in the rural and urban areas (Ingle & Nath, 2008).

According to a study, (Tao and McRoy, 2015) shortage of hospital beds is one of the major concerns for providing more complex care to the elderly with chronic or comorbid health conditions while they are living at home. At the same time, an aging population also reduces the availability of family caregivers. The problem is especially critical in societies, such as China and India, where there has been both rapid aging of the population and a tradition that children are the primary caregivers for their elderly parents who are no longer independent.

To effectively care for the aging population, nurses entering the workforce must be adept at managing complex conditions including acute episodes of one or more chronic conditions, facilitating transitions in care, identifying real or potential risks, gaps in care, and waste. They must capably devise strategies for improvement, tracking progress over time and making adjustments as needed. Often overlooked in nursing curricula is the complexity of caring for older adults with co-morbidities and the attendant ethical questions about care and treatment. In many nursing programs, curricula remain focused on acute, episodic care with clinical experiences concentrating on specific disease processes or the skills students can perform in the provision of care (Ironside, 2010)

Physical design means the observable built environment and all its architectural features. This includes the physical configuration, equipment, furnishings, and décor that together impede or enhance an older person’s independent function (Ulrich, 2004). Elements of physical design are reflected, for example, in the degree of stress experienced when determining the location and route to a treatment setting; the amount of privacy offered to patients and families; and how easily patients understand signage and find their way around the building.

The physical environment of the hospital has been built to support the technology and equipment needed by health care professionals to do their work. This environment enables physicians and other health care professionals to deal efficiently with the patient’s acute physiological problems using a scientific objective paradigm to treat the disease, and attempt to cure it. The hospital environment creates stress in older adults by challenging their adaptive ability. The unfamiliar hospital environment, with its medical jargon, unfamiliar equipment, and disruption of life-long routines and habits, are significant sources of stress.. The older person, when frail, ill, and weak has less energy to manage and cope with the demands of hospitalization (Parke, 2007).

According to Eric Coleman, Patients with complex care needs who require care across different health care settings are vulnerable to experiencing serious quality problems. A care transitions intervention designed to encourage patients and their caregivers to assert a more active role during care transitions may reduce rehospitalisation rates (Coleman, 2006).

A study conducted showed that there was significant difference in Geriatric depression scale between women who participated in the older women support group and the ones who didn’t. The result also showed that the incidence of depression was less among the women who participated in the older women support group compared to that of those who didn’t. Also the level of well being was higher in the women who attended the older women support groups (Segrist, 2008).

Higgs P says that gerontological literature suggests that an adjusted built environment is needed in hospital to support a different approach to providing acute care for older people.(Higgs, 1998). At present, the organizational culture in hospitals is technologically dependent on an expert model that deals with short-term, acute biologically-based illnesses. Hospital customs and traditions shaped by this agenda place time-limited, acute interventions ahead of chronic health interventions. In contrast, older people typically require simultaneous treatment for three or four different chronic health problems along with any acute problems. These patients require a multi-disciplinary, holistic and more humanistic approach to care, more intensive rehabilitation, and a longer recovery time. Dominance of the acute care agenda obscures older peoples’ chronic health and functional needs, placing them at risk for poor clinical and social outcomes. To address the special needs of older people, a gerontologically sensitive physical environment should be proposed.

III: Research objectives and Methodology

Statement of the problem: Feasibility for Setting Up Geriatric Care Services in A Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital

Objectives of the study: To study the feasibility to set up a Geriatric department in a selected hospital

Research approach: The study was conducted using a descriptive cross sectional type research design. The primary data collection was done through structured questionnaire administered to the management representatives as well as to the doctors of the selected teaching hospital.

Sampling and sampling techniques: A sample size of 104 doctors, and 3 management representatives were selected using purposive sampling technique based on the following sample size calculation formula.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

N = Total number of subjects

Doctors (140)

e = Allowable error

Doctor (5%)

Tools and techniques of data collection: The study was conducted using a structured close-ended questionnaire to collect the data from doctors and management representatives.

Data collection method: A structured questionnaire was developed and administered on the doctors and the management representatives to assess the feasibility to set up a Geriatric Care Services in A Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital

Inclusion criteria: Doctors working in the Out Patient Department were included in this study.

The administrator, assistant administrator and the quality manager were considered as the management representatives for the study

Limitations of the study: The study was limited only to doctors and management representatives of the selected hospital.

Content validity: The tool was given to experts for content validity. Based on their suggestions and recommendations, the tool was modified.

Plan for data analysis: The collected data was analyzed by frequency, percentage, mean, Standard Deviation based on objectives of the study. The data was presented graphically as well as in the form of tables.

IV: Data analysis and Result:

This section deals with the analysis and interpretation of the data collected through structured questionnaire from 104 doctors and 3 management representatives to assess the feasibility for setting up Geriatric care services in a tertiary care teaching hospital. The results obtained from the analysis were represented in the form of tables and graphs in two sections: Part A -Deals with demographic data of the doctors and Part B- Deals with feasibility analysis of doctors and management to set up Geriatric care services in a tertiary care teaching hospital.

Part A: Demographic Data of the Doctors: Our study data showed that majority of the doctors who had participated in this study were between the age group 23-30 years. 26% of the respondents were between the age group 31-40 years of age (**Figure 1**). The gender wise distribution of the doctors showed that majority of the doctors (54.8%) were male and 45.2% of the respondents were female (**Figure 2**). The study data showed that 52.9% of the doctors who had participated in our study had work experience of 1-2 years and 20.2% of the respondents had more than 5 years of work experience (**Figure 3**). Our study showed that 33.7% of the respondents were post graduates and 24% of the respondents were MBBS graduates. This showed that the upcoming medical generation has understood the need for specialized care for the elderly (**Figure 4**).

Figure 1: Age wise distribution of doctors

Figure 2: Gender wise distribution of doctors

Figure 3: Experience wise distribution of doctors

Figure 4: Qualification wise distribution of doctors

Part B: Feasibility analysis of opinion of doctors and management to set up Geriatric care services in a tertiary care teaching hospital: Our study showed that 100% and 95.2% of the management representatives and doctors respectively opined that a geriatric unit will improve the service quality provided for the elderly people. 2 out of 3 management representatives opined that a geriatric unit will result in reduction in inappropriate bed blocking, help in targeting high risk patients and if the geriatric unit is established successfully the hospital will receive greater recognition for the achievement made. 90.4% of the doctors opined that a geriatric unit will help in targeting of appropriate high risk patients and if the unit is implemented successfully the hospital will receive greater recognition for the achievements made (**Table 1**).

PATIENT CENTRIC CARE AND QUALITY					
SL NO	PARTICULARS	DOCTORS		MANAGEMENT	
		FREQUENCY	%	FREQUENCY	%
1	A geriatric unit will result in reduction in inappropriate use of acute care hospital beds by reducing bed blocking	80	76.9	2	66.7
2	A geriatric unit will help in targeting of appropriate high risk patients	94	90.4	2	66.7
3	Implementing a geriatric unit will lead to decrease in the number of patients for non – geriatric physicians and specialists	67	64.4	1	33.3
4	If implemented successfully the hospital will receive greater recognition for the achievements made	94	90.4	2	66.7
5	A geriatric unit will improve the service quality provided for the elderly people	99	95.2	3	100.0

Table 1: Doctors and Management response regarding feasibility of setting up geriatric care services in a tertiary care teaching hospital with regard Patient centric care and quality.

Table 2 shows that 2 out of 3 management representatives opined that setting up a geriatric unit is expensive. 2 out of 3 management representatives and 77.9% of the doctors opined that a geriatric unit will increase the patient statistics and revenue of the hospital.66.3% of the doctors opined that setting up a geriatric unit is profitable to the organization.

Table 2: Doctors and Management response regarding feasibility of setting up geriatric care services in a tertiary care teaching hospital with regard to finance

FINANCE					
SL NO	PARTICULARS	DOCTORS		MANAGEMENT	
		FREQUENCY	%	FREQUENCY	%
1	Setting up of a geriatric unit is expensive	61	58.7	2	66.7
2	The institute will receive monetary benefits from the government for the implementation of the elderly care unit	62	59.6	33.3	33.3
3	Setting up a geriatric unit is profitable to the organization	69	66.3	1	33.3
4	The hospital will be able to get the return on investment for the geriatric unit in a short period of time	44	42.3	1	33.3
5	A geriatric unit will increase the patient statistics and revenue of the hospital	81	77.9	2	66.7

Table 3: Doctors and Management response regarding feasibility of setting up geriatric care services in a tertiary care teaching hospital with regard to manpower

MANPOWER					
SL NO	PARTICULARS	DOCTORS		MANAGEMENT	
		FREQUENCY	%	FREQUENCY	%
1	Implementation of diagnostic and care plans with involvement of general practitioners is easy with a geriatric unit	70	67.3	1	33.3
2	A geriatric setup will increase the demand for geriatric physicians	94	90.4	2	66.7
3	There is a need for recruiting additional manpower in order to meet the requirements of a geriatric department	91	87.5	3	100.0
4	Experienced and specialized geriatric specialists are available in our hospital	40	38.5	1	33.3

Table 3 shows that 90.4% of the doctors and 2 out of 3 management representatives opined that a geriatric setup will increase the demand for geriatric physicians. 100% of the management representatives and 87.5% of the doctors opined that there is a need for recruiting additional manpower in order to meet the requirements of a geriatric department.

Our study shows that 94.2% of the doctors and 100% of the management representatives opined that a well-built geriatric unit will make the stay of the patients more comfortable. Also 76.9% of the doctors and 100% of the management representatives opined that there is a need for structural changes of the hospital in order to set up a geriatric unit. 1 out of 3 management representatives and 42.3% of the doctors had agreed and suggested a feasible location to setup a geriatric unit in the hospital out of which 97.7% of the doctors agreed that the feasible location that they suggested to setup a geriatric unit is accessible to the patients. Hence we can conclude that with the necessary structural changes it is feasible to setup a specialized geriatric care service in the hospital (**Table 4**).

Table 4: Doctors and Management response regarding feasibility of setting up a geriatric department with regard to infrastructure

INFRASTRUCTURE					
SL NO	PARTICULARS	DOCTORS		MANAGEMENT	
		FREQUENCY	%	FREQUENCY	%
1	There is a need for structural changes of the hospital in order to set up a geriatric unit	80	76.9	3	100.0
2	A well-built geriatric unit will make the stay of the patients more comfortable	98	94.2	3	100.0
3	There is a feasible location to setup a geriatric unit in the hospital.	44	42.3	1	33.3
4	The location available to setup a geriatric unit is accessible to the patients	43	97.7	1	100.0
5	The developed infrastructural facilities in the new geriatric setup will ensure patient safety.	87	83.7	2	66.7
6	The space and infrastructure makes it feasible to set up a geriatric unit in the hospital	83	79.8	2	66.7

V: Interpretation of the data

The aim of this study is to study the feasibility to set up a Geriatric Care Service in a selected tertiary care teaching hospital. The data was collected through structured questionnaire administered to 104 doctors and 3 management representatives.

Demographic data of doctors: 65.4% of the doctors were between 23-30 years of age, 26% of the doctors were between 31-40 years of age and the remaining doctors were above 41 years of age. Out of 104 doctors 54.8% of the doctors were male and 45.2% of the doctors were female. The collected data showed that 52.9% of the doctors had 1-2 years of work experience, 20.2% of the doctors had above 5 years of work experience, 18.3% of the doctors had work experience of 2-3 years and the remaining doctors had work experience between 3-5 years. 24% of the doctors were MBBS graduates, 33.7% of the doctors were PG students, 15.4% of the doctors were MD and MS graduates and 11.5% of the doctors had other qualifications such as MCH, DM etc.

Doctors and management representative's perspective on feasibility of setting up a Geriatric Care Service:

A) *Patient centric care and quality*: 100% and 95.2% of the management representatives and doctors respectively opined that a geriatric unit will improve the service quality provided for the elderly people. 2 out of 3 management representatives opined that a geriatric unit will result in reduction in inappropriate bed blocking, help in targeting high

risk patients and if the geriatric unit is established successfully the hospital will receive greater recognition for the achievement made. 90.4% of the doctors opined that a geriatric unit will help in targeting of appropriate high risk patients and if the unit is implemented successfully the hospital will receive greater recognition for the achievements made.

B) Financial feasibility: 2 out of 3 management representatives opined that setting up Geriatric Care service is expensive. 2 out of 3 management representatives and 77.9% of the doctors opined that a geriatric unit will increase the patient statistics and revenue of the hospital. 66.3% of the doctors opined that setting up a geriatric unit is profitable to the organization.

C) Manpower feasibility: 90.4% of the doctors and 2 out of 3 management representatives opined that a geriatric setup will increase the demand for geriatric physicians. 100% of the management representatives and 87.5% of the doctors opined that there is a need for recruiting additional manpower in order to meet the requirements of a geriatric department.

D) Infrastructure feasibility: The collected data shows that 94.2% of the doctors and 100% of the management representatives opined that a well-built geriatric unit will make the stay of the patients more comfortable. Also 76.9% of the doctors and 100% of the management representatives opined that there is a need for structural changes of the hospital in order to set up a geriatric unit.

VI: Findings

The study was conducted in order to study the feasibility to set up Geriatric Care services in the selected tertiary care teaching hospital from the perspective of doctors and management representatives. The findings of the study are as follows:

- 93.3% of the doctors and 100% of the management representatives said that if the hospital provides pick up and drop facilities for the geriatric patients then it will help in increasing the patient inflow.
- Many of the doctors and management representatives agree that a geriatric unit will help in reducing functional decline.
- 90.4 % of the doctors and 66.4% of the management representatives agreed that a geriatric unit will help in targeting of appropriate high risk patients and if implemented successfully the hospital will receive greater recognition for the achievements made.
- 42.3% of the doctors and 33.3% of the management representatives said that there is a feasible location in the selected hospital in order to set up a geriatric department and that location is easily accessible to the patients.
- The data showed that the respondents had suggested a suitable location for setting up a geriatric department in a selected hospital. The locations suggested were, any part of the general wards, part of physiotherapy OPD, part of the health card section or the attached leprosy hospital.

VII: Suggestions

The study was conducted in order to assess the study the feasibility to set up Geriatric Care services in the selected tertiary care teaching hospital from the perspective of doctors and management representatives and following measures are suggested:

- A large number of geriatric populations are currently utilizing the health services at the selected hospital. Hence if a separate department is set up for the sole use of the geriatric population, it will be well occupied and utilized.
- A fully fledged geriatric department is not set up in any of the hospitals in the district. If one is established in the selected hospital, then it will definitely increase the patient statistics and goodwill of the hospital and also receive recognition.
- The study shows that overall all the doctors and management representatives are in the favour of setting up a geriatric department in the selected hospital. Hence we can expect co-operation from the hospital staff while establishing a geriatric department.
- A new geriatric department will increase the scope for geriatric medicine in the area. This will attract a lot of prospectus for the aspiring gerontologists and geriatric specialists.
- Following structural changes has to be made in a new geriatric department
 - 1) The interiors should be very soothing and should brighten up the place.
 - 2) The areas should be made geriatric friendly by installing safety measures like hand rails, bed rails, bed side call bell, etc.
 - 3) Designing a relaxation garden so that the ambulatory patients can spend some time out of their beds in order to relax and rejuvenate.
- Along with a geriatric OPD and in- patient set up a geriatric day care centre also can be setup where in the elderly people can enrol themselves in the programs conducted by the department in order to take part in contemporary

geriatric health care activities like yoga/ meditation, walking groups, bone builders programme, scheduled exercise programmes, older women support group etc.

VIII: Conclusion

A well-established healthcare facility which prioritizes the care for the elderly helps a person to be less dependable on their family members in order to avail the basic health care requirements. This will bring in a sense of independence and increase self-dignity of the elderly people which will in turn increase their emotional quality of life. This study concluded that according to the doctors and management representatives, elderly patients require separate health care setup with all the facilities and services and that a geriatric unit will help in targeting high risk patients. Based on the opinion of the doctors and management representatives, there is a feasible location in the selected hospital in order to set up a geriatric department and that location is easily accessible to the patients. Hence establishment of a well-equipped geriatric service care unit is feasible in the selected tertiary care teaching hospital.

REFERENCES:

1. Coleman, E. A., Parry, C., Chalmers, S., & Min, S. J. (2006). The care transitions intervention: results of a randomized controlled trial. *Archives of internal medicine*, 166(17), 1822-1828.
2. Higgs P.(1996). The old age challenge to the biomedical model: Paradigm strain and health policy-Longino, C., Murphy, J. *Ageing & Society*, 16(1):118-9.
3. Ingle, G. K., & Nath, A. (2008). Geriatric health in India: Concerns and solutions. *Indian journal of community medicine: official publication of Indian Association of Preventive & Social Medicine*, 33(4), 214.
4. Ironside, P. M., Tagliareni, M. E., McLaughlin, B., King, E., & Mengel, A. (2010). Fostering geriatrics in associate degree nursing education: An assessment of current curricula and clinical experiences. *Journal of Nursing Education*, 49(5), 246-251.
5. Lewis, D. (2008). Organization design for geriatrics: an evidence based approach. *Regional Geriatric Programs of Ontario*.
6. Parke B. (2007). *Physical Design Dimension of an Elder Friendly Hospital: An evidence-based practice review undertaken for the Vancouver Island Health Authority*. University of Victoria.10p
7. Segrist, K. A. (2008). Impact of support groups on well-being of older women. *Journal of Gerontological Social Work*, 51(1-2), 42-52.
8. Tao, H., & McRoy, S. (2015). Caring for and keeping the elderly in their homes. *Chinese Nursing Research*, 2(2-3), 31-34.
9. Ulrich, R., Zimring, C., Quan, X., Joseph, A., & Choudhary, R. (2004). *The role of the physical environment in the hospital of the 21st century: A once-in-a-lifetime opportunity*. Concord, CA: The Center for Health Design, 3.

